

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. There are many analyses and studies in various scientific literature on the role and impact of using technologies in teaching English. The work carried out on this topic shows how technologies help to improve the language teaching process, how they increase students' motivation to learn, and how they create opportunities for teachers to use new methods. Technologies, such as mobile applications, online courses, interactive platforms, and gamification elements, provide students with the opportunity to consolidate and develop their knowledge. All this supports the independent learning process of students, creating the most effective and interesting learning environment for them. At the same time, technologies introduce teachers to new methodological approaches, help personalize lessons and adapt to the needs of students.

Key words: technology, innovation, interactivity, gamification, mobile application, online education, E-learning, blended learning, learning platform, motivation.

РОЛЬ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В различной научной литературе имеется множество анализов и исследований о роли и влиянии технологий на обучение

английскому языку. Работа по этой теме показывает, как технологии могут помочь улучшить процесс обучения языку, как они могут повысить мотивацию учащихся к обучению и как они могут создать для учителей возможности использовать новые методы. Такие технологии, как мобильные приложения, онлайн-курсы, интерактивные платформы и элементы геймификации, позволяют студентам укреплять и развивать свои знания. Все это поддерживает самостоятельный процесс обучения студентов и создает для них максимально эффективную и интересную среду обучения. При этом технологии знакомят учителей с новыми методическими подходами, помогают персонализировать уроки и адаптироваться к потребностям учащихся.

Ключевые слова: технологии, инновации, интерактивность, геймификация, мобильное приложение, онлайн-образование, электронное обучение, смешанное обучение, учебная платформа, мотивация

Introduction

The role of technology in teaching English has become an integral part of every education system today. Initially, the use of technology in teaching methods has created many new opportunities for teachers. Mobile applications, online courses, video lessons and interactive learning platforms facilitate communication between teachers and students, making the teaching process more effective and interesting. With the help of technology, students have the opportunity to learn in their own time, attend classes from anywhere and at any time. In addition, the role of technology in teaching English is not limited to just enlivening classes. They also allow students to personalize the language learning process.

For example, with the help of various educational applications and online platforms, students can analyze their strengths and weaknesses and choose learning methods that suit them. Also, systems based on artificial intelligence analyze students' mistakes and provide appropriate recommendations for correcting them. Interactive lessons and learning materials ensure active participation of students. For example, through videos, audio materials, educational games and quizzes, students not only absorb information, but also have the opportunity to apply the learned knowledge in practice.

This increases students' motivation in learning English. Technology also allows teachers to better monitor and evaluate student results. With the help of online tests, quizzes and in-class activities, teachers can accurately assess the level of knowledge of students and make necessary changes. At the same time, technology in teaching English also helps to increase students' cultural literacy. Through online resources, students can get acquainted with texts written in different English languages, learn about different cultures. This, in turn, motivates them to learn English more deeply. Thus, technologies are of great help not only to students but also to teachers in learning English. Their increasing role in the educational process is taking the quality of education to a new level.

In this article, we will analyze in detail the new opportunities that are emerging in teaching English using technologies and how they affect the educational process. Nowadays, many conditions have been created for learning foreign languages. Especially there are many ways to learn online. To organize these foreign languages various sites on the internet will help you closely. For example, it is useful in learning English Sites that are: **List-english.ru** -various materials for learning English: online dictionaries, schools, forums, translators,

tutors, tests, school textbooks, video courses, games, Android Apps, iPhone, YouTube channels, podcasts, and more. Everything is free. **Englishtips.org** - Downloadable textbooks and books. The search engine is good works. You can find many things related to language learning. **British council.org** is the website of the British Council. Tests, grammar, games and others. Everything is in English, so it's a bit much for those new to the language it will be difficult to navigate, but knowledge will be strengthened through this. **Real-english.com** is a site full of lessons, articles and videos. **Eslpod.com** -Its main mission is to teach English as a second language. Advantages of technology: Ease and Convenience: You can learn anytime and anywhere. Affordability: Many apps and resources are available for free or at low cost. Efficiency: With the help of games, interactive exercises and technology, language can be learned quickly and efficiently. Personalization: Many apps and resources provide curriculum tailored to the needs of the learner. Things to consider when using technology: student motivation is important. Technology by itself does not guarantee language learning. Real communication is also important. Technology is only an additional tool, and language exchange with real people is also necessary. You should not be completely dependent on technology. You can also get information about the language you are learning from books, magazines, and other resources. The role of technology in teaching English has been increasing in recent years. Initially, technologies were used only in a few schools and universities, but now they have been widely introduced throughout the education system. These technologies create many new opportunities for teachers and students, helping to improve the quality and efficiency of education. Let's consider several main areas of teaching English with the help of technology.

The role of technology in modernizing the educational process Technologies, for example, help make the educational process more efficient and convenient with the help of mobile applications, interactive platforms, video lessons, and online tests. Students can independently study lessons, review materials online, and receive assessments in a timely manner. Through mobile applications, for example, with the help of programs such as **Duolingo, Babbel, and Memrise**, it is possible to create an interesting and interactive environment for learning English. Increasing student motivation with the help of technology, students have the opportunity to monitor and manage their language learning process. Online platforms have special assessment systems, tests and educational games for students, which create motivation for students to achieve goals. For example, gamification (the use of game elements) technologies can be used to involve students in the process and make lessons interesting. Personalized Learning Technologies allow students to choose lesson materials that suit their needs. Personalized learning methods analyze students' knowledge levels and offer the most effective and appropriate materials for them. For example, distance learning platforms and online courses allow students to learn at their own pace, while paying attention to the individual needs of students. Use of multimedia resources Using video, audio and other multimedia resources through technology in teaching English makes education more interactive and interesting. Audio and video materials help develop listening and comprehension skills, while also allowing students to understand different accents and cultures. For example, through English language teaching channels and films and TV series on YouTube, the language learning process becomes more realistic and practical. Distance learning and online courses Distance learning and online courses create opportunities for the widespread use of technology in teaching English. Such courses provide students with

the opportunity to learn English anywhere and at any time. Online courses, such as platforms such as **Coursera, Udemy, edX, Future Learn**, allow students to gain the necessary knowledge in teaching English, complete interactive exercises and communicate with teachers. Teaching with **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and robots.**

Technologies, especially with the help of artificial intelligence (AI) and robots, are creating new opportunities in teaching English. Teachers, chatbots, and language learning support systems based on artificial intelligence help students identify and correct their mistakes. AI systems are able to analyze students' mistakes, correct them, and provide individual recommendations to students. Such technologies develop students' ability to learn independently. Effective time management and individualized study of lessons. Technologies can help students manage the process of learning English more effectively. Students allocate their time to studying lessons, and at the same time, they have the opportunity to review learning materials or refer to additional resources.

Distance learning systems and online platforms provide students with the opportunity to manage their time and independently organize the learning process. New methodological approaches for teachersTechnology in teaching English allows teachers to use newmethodological approaches. For example, with the help of online tests, interactive lesson materials, and various programs, teachers have the opportunity to assess students' knowledge and quickly analyze the results. This helps teachers identify students'strengths and weaknesses and allows them to teach them through a personalized approach. The role of technology in teaching English is expanding in all directions. With the help of technology, interactive and personalized learning opportunities are createdfor students, increasing their motivation to learn. Technology also

allows teachers to effectively assess students, present lesson materials in a more interesting and accurate way. Today, technology plays an important role in introducing changes in English teaching, improving the quality of education, and creating opportunities for students to study more effectively.

Discussion

We can see that the role of technology in teaching English has become an integral part of the modern educational process. The use of technology in the education system is an important factor in increasing the level of knowledge of students and improving the effectiveness of education, which requires an analysis of various aspects, positive and negative aspects of this process. First, technology allows students to learn independently. Online courses, mobile applications and interactive lessons give students the opportunity to develop independently.

Students have the opportunity to manage their time, personalize their learning and consolidate their knowledge more. This is especially important for individual students, since each student learns at a different pace, and technology provides them with materials that suit their needs. At the same time, making lessons interesting and interactive with the help of technology increases student motivation. Distance learning, video lessons, interactive quizzes and gamification elements further increase students' interest in learning English. This is especially important for the new generation of students, as they are more interested in technology and perceive this process as a new form of learning. However, there are also some negative aspects of using technology.

For example, teaching with the help of technology can hinder students' development of face-to-face communication skills in society. Online learning systems and video lessons can reduce students' social contacts, limit students' ability to express their opinions in face-to-face communication and work in groups. This issue is especially relevant for younger students, since the development of social skills is very important for them. In addition, dependence on technology can also cause negative situations. Many students rely too much on technology, seeing it as the only tool in the learning process. In this case, students become passive in using technology, spending time only on learning platforms or applications rather than learning. Also, students with limited access to the Internet may find it difficult to use technology, which can lead to educational inequalities. To effectively use technology in teaching English, teachers need to constantly update their methodologies. Successfully integrating new technologies into the teaching process creates the opportunity to provide students with innovative and interactive materials. However, to use technology correctly, it is necessary to train teachers and familiarize them with new tools and platforms. At the same time, teachers need to know how to adapt and use technology effectively in their lessons. Conclusion the use of technology in teaching English significantly increases the effectiveness of the educational process. With the help of technology, students' learning process becomes more interactive, personalized and motivationally strong. Students can independently learn and quickly evaluate the results of learning English through mobile applications, online platforms, video lessons and gamification elements. This increases students' interest in the language learning process and allows them to choose the most effective methods.

At the same time, technology creates opportunities for teachers to use new methodological approaches, personalize lessons and adapt them to

the individual needs of students. Distance learning and online courses allow students to learn English anywhere and at any time, which makes the educational process more convenient. However, the use of technology in education may have some negative aspects. Students' social interactions, over-reliance on technology, and inequities for students with limited access to technology can occur. Therefore, it is important to train teachers and use technology wisely to successfully integrate technology into the classroom. In general, technology in English teaching can improve the quality of education, increase students' interest in learning, and allow teachers to manage lessons effectively. The rational and correct use of technology further develops the educational process and increases students' success in learning English.

Conclusion

The role of technology in English teaching is very important in the modern educational process. Technology creates opportunities for students to self-study, independently acquire knowledge, and personalize the learning process. With the help of online platforms, mobile applications, and interactive lessons, students can work more effectively, interestingly, and motivatedly in learning English. Technology also allows teachers to modernize lessons, use new methods, and adapt to the individual needs of students. However, there are some negative aspects to using technology in the educational process. It can lead to a decrease in students' social interaction in society, excessive reliance on technology, and inequalities for students with limited access to technology. Therefore, it is necessary to use technology effectively and wisely. Introducing teachers to new technologies and successfully integrating them into the educational process will help improve the quality of education. In general, technology plays an important role in teaching English, making the learning

process more effective and interactive for students. They can further improve the education system, develop students' learning skills, and allow teachers to use new methods. The successful use of technology in the educational process will lead to an increase in the quality of education and further enhance students' success in learning English.

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